

Major William Gibboney Biography by Brian Paul Kaess

Major William Gibboney was born June 26, 1815, in County Tyrone, Ireland, to Thomas Gibboney and Margaret Kyle, being the sixth of seven children. The Gibboney's were an Irish family hailing from Omaugh, Co. Tyrone, Ireland, and the family parish and townland is believed to be Drumnakilly. They were of Anglican faith. They came to America abt 1815-1817, traveling through the Port of New York and settled in Wytheville, Virginia, where the family achieved some prominence there.

He married Francis Ann Haller in 1841, and, after her death, he was a widower for a short time, before he married his cousin, Caroline Ann Kyle in 1843. His 1st wife was Lutheran, like many of her sisters who also intermarried with the Gibboney's. From the 1st marriage was born a son Albert Haller Gibboney, and from his 2nd wife Caroline was born nine more children: David Kyle, Virginia Kyle, Jane Kyle, James Kyle, Margaret Henry, William Jr., Carolyn Lafayette, Thomas G, & Thomas McCausland Gibboney.

During the American Civil War (ACW), both William Gibboney and his brother Robert Gibboney were responsible for making Wytheville, Virginia, a major confederate supply depot, per Dr. Mark Baldwin, a cousin. Confederate Home Guard were manning one of William's houses during the Wytheville Raid (1863), aka Toland's Raid, and it is said that a bullet that killed Union Colonel John Toland was fired from his house. The Union subsequently evacuated Gibboney's house and put it to flames. He shows up in many Confederate supply depositions, himself first being an Assistant Quarter Master (AQM), and then Quarter Master (QM) in Wytheville for 'Johnny Reb' during the war.

After the war, William Gibboney received, like his brother Robert, a Confederate Presidential Pardon from Pres. Andrew Johnson, Lincoln's successor. He appears in many records, both before, during and after the war. He embarked on a mercantile career and was a dry goods merchant in Wytheville for many years and may have even expanded his operations to such a point that he had a business or two out of state, like in North Carolina, where he had extended family. Prior to the war, one account says 'he was one of the wealthiest and influential citizens in the southwest.' During the *antebellum* period, he appears to have owned a handful of slaves. He also appears in the Confederate Officer's Card Index and Freedman's Bureau records. The growth of his family is well-attested in various records.

He died on Friday, December 13, 1901, and is buried in Wytheville, Virginia, at St. John's Lutheran Church Cemetery Sauers. His cause of death was pneumonia, and he fell ill for a short time preceding his passing. He was survived by eight children. Capt. Gibboney was 'a man of sterling integrity and was connected with many of the most prominent internal improvements of the southwest.'